

THE IMPORTANCE OF INTELLECTUAL RESOURCES IN THE MANIFESTATION OF IDEAS ABOUT PSYCHOLOGICAL HELP IN STUDENTS

Matniyozova Markhabo Abdugapporovna

Psychologist of Urganch State Pedagogical Institute

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Abstract: In this thesis, opinions are given about the scientific-theoretical basis and importance of using intellectual resources in the formation and manifestation of students' ideas about psychological help.

Key words: critical thinking, intellectual resource, educational system, Intervention, technology, Stress, psychological support.

Introduction:

Psychological assistance to student youth is a relatively new humanitarian discipline, the emergence of which is associated with a number of factors of modern life: the globalization of higher education, the increase in neuropsychic stress in students, both of which are rapidly changing educational programs. the need for adaptation and a flexible labor market, etc. The school of psychological services and centers inevitably raised the issue of developing the conceptual framework of psychological support as a type of psychologist's activity in a specific educational environment.

The complexity of developing a model of psychological support for students is related to the heterogeneity and multi-directionality of various schools of counseling and psychotherapy based on it, which leads to problems when trying to create a methodology for practice. Even in countries where psychological services have existed for a long time, there is no agreed model for providing psychological support to student youth and does not exist, because all professionals base their work on different theoretical foundations¹.

Providing psychological support to students is an important issue in educational institutions. The main purpose of this support is to strengthen the mental health of students, to eliminate stress, depression or other psychological problems that may arise during the study. Below are some key aspects of providing psychological support to students:

Personal Counseling: Through private counseling, students can openly discuss their problems and find personal solutions. In this process, psychologists help them understand their feelings and gain self-awareness.

¹ Yanchuk, V.A. Methodology, theory and method in modern social psychology and personology: an integrative-eclectic approach / V.A. Yanchuk. - Minsk: Bestprint, 2000. - 416 p.

Group Sessions: Sometimes students can learn from each other's experiences. Group sessions are a great opportunity to share experiences, support and develop social skills.

Stress Management: University life can be stressful. Psychologists teach students stress management techniques, such as meditation, breathing exercises, and time management strategies.

Educational seminars and events: Educational institutions organize seminars and events to educate and raise awareness about psychological health. Through these activities, students can feel good about themselves and learn more about the importance of mental health.

Emergency Services: In some cases, students may need immediate assistance. Therefore, many educational institutions provide emergency psychological support services. In general, psychological support for students is an important and necessary service for students in educational institutions. This support has a positive impact on their academic success, personal development and overall well-being.

Psychological features of using intellectual resources:

The psychological characteristics of the use of intellectual resources, that is, the psychological aspects of the effective use of intellectual assets such as information, knowledge, and skills, include:

Ability to Analyze Data: The ability to extract and analyze important data is required for the proper use of intellectual resources. It means searching for the necessary knowledge in specific situations and applying it to make practical decisions.

Creative Thinking: Creative thinking is essential for developing new ideas and finding unconventional solutions to existing problems. This allows for the best use of available resources.

Prioritize Learning: Continuous learning and updating one's knowledge is an important part of effective use of intellectual resources. This includes familiarization with new technologies and methodologies².

Critical Thinking: Critically evaluating information and determining its reliability plays an important role in the use of intellectual resources. This ensures that false or misleading information is avoided.

Motivation and Purpose: To achieve your goals requires planning and discipline to use the intellectual resources you need.

² Olifirovich, N.I. Psychological service of the university: features of advisory activity / N. Olifirovich // Bulletin of Brestskaga University. – Series 3. Philology, Pedagogy, Psychology. - No. 2, 2010. - P.132-141.

Collaborate with a Team: Often, effective use of intellectual resources is achieved through teamwork. This requires collaborating with people with different skills and using their knowledge.

Time and Resource Management: When using intellectual resources, it is important to effectively manage time and other resources, as these resources may be limited. These skills and characteristics are necessary for the best use of intellectual resources, and their development and improvement are possible through continuous learning and practice.

Summary:

Today, we often hear about the concept of psychological help. The reason for this is that on the basis of psychological support, it is possible to control the emotional state of people, shape and direct their psychological characteristics. One of the main goals of higher education is to form ideas about psychological help, especially among students. Intellectual resources are very important in students' perceptions of psychological support.

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